

INCREASING OF QUALIFICATIONS IN LIFELONG EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE PERSONALITY OF THE TEACHER

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Annotation: The system of advanced training of educators is considered as a center for continuous education of a teacher, assuming a consistent alternation of educational activities with his practical professional activities. The main purpose of the advanced training system is revealed - it is the development of a teacher as a person and as a specialist, a professional with a deep understanding of the socio-cultural and educational situation.

Key words: advanced training system for educators, qualifications, professional training of teachers, advanced training, advanced training functions, organizational and substantive principles of advanced training.

Introduction. The system of advanced training of educators of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the subsystems of continuous education of a teacher. This system is considered as a process of continuous development of a person, that is, "a process that takes place throughout a person's life and is aimed at the most complete disclosure of his abilities in intellectual, moral, spiritual terms, a process consisting of basic and subsequent education and involving, at the second stage, a consistent alternation of educational activities in the system of specially created institutions with social and practical activities in the field of professional labor" [1, 2]. But many scientists pay attention to the fact that in recent years there has been a clear narrowing of the significance of the educational impact of institutions of the

advanced training system on the development of the personality of the teacher, his value and professional interests [3, 4, 5].

Pedagogical postgraduate education, as the education of adults, should contribute to the personal and professional development of the teacher on the basis of "the axiological foundation of education for the sustainable development of the system of post-material values" and "the formation of the humanitarian culture of the teacher" [9, 10, 12].

The system of advanced training of educators is defined by domestic scientists as:

- a set of educational institutions of additional education in various organizational and legal forms that implement additional pedagogical professional advanced training programs with the aim of increasing professionalism and competence, mastering new functional duties without obtaining a new specialty [6];
- type of additional professional education, renewal and deepening of previously acquired professional knowledge, improvement of the business qualities of employees, satisfaction of their educational needs related to professional activities [6, 8];
- the center of lifelong education and personal development, carrying out an all-round increase in the level of education and development of individuals [7].

The system of advanced training of teaching staff in the Republic of Uzbekistan is characterized as multi-level, and the structure of professional advanced training is similar to the components of an integral system of additional professional education for adults: advanced training, professional retraining and internships [12, 13, 14]. The fundamental principles of a multi-level system for advanced training of teaching staff are:

- continuity of advanced training throughout the entire period of pedagogical activity;

- the advanced nature of advanced training, taking into account the prospects for the development of the educational system, the achievements of pedagogical science and current pedagogical experience;
- a combination of federal approaches with a broad initiative of local educational authorities;
- consistency and continuity of the functioning of various parts of the advanced training system [15, 18, 19].

The main functions of teacher training in the system of professional pedagogical education are diagnostic, compensatory, cognitive, prognostic, and adaptive [16, 17].

The diagnostic function is the determination of abilities, the identification of individual psychological characteristics and the level of preparedness.

The compensatory function is the elimination of gaps in education associated with the obsolescence of previously acquired knowledge, with the lack of psychological and pedagogical knowledge in the process of vocational education, with the importance of deep mastery of professional knowledge and skills.

The cognitive function is the satisfaction of the professional, intellectual and informational needs of the teacher's personality.

The prognostic function is the development of creative potential, identifying the teacher's readiness for professional pedagogical activity.

The adaptive function is the development of information culture, teaching self-education, the skills of designing universal pedagogical technologies and systems necessary for orientation in activities when changing the status of an educational institution, training profile, position, place of work.

Thus, the system of advanced training of educators is a type of additional professional education in which educational activities gradually alternate with the social and practical activities of a teacher in order to update, deepen previously acquired professional knowledge, improve business skills, master new functional

duties without obtaining a new specialty and meeting the educational needs associated with professional activities [20]. The leading direction for the system of advanced training of teaching staff is continuous professional development throughout the entire period of pedagogical activity and the development of the teacher's personality, identifying his readiness for professional pedagogical activity, and developing his creative potential. A creative approach to the learning process in the system of professional development for teachers not only provides certain information, but develops the creative abilities of the teacher, his ability to learn new things and apply them in practice [21].

Thus, "qualification" is the level of professional training of a specialist, and the level of mastery of knowledge, the range and breadth of knowledge and skills, the ability to perform special tasks, the ability to rationally organize and plan one's work, the ability to use knowledge in non-standard situations.

Qualification is a constant within which his professional qualities exist and remain, and the leading indicator in assessing the complexity of a teacher's work, which is the basis for the standardization of education.

And the indicator of labor productivity is pedagogical skill. The qualification acquired by a teacher is seen as a set of professional knowledge and skills that must be dynamically updated as new pedagogical technologies develop.

The concept of "teacher training" in the theory and practice of pedagogical science is understood as:

- professional and pedagogical training, aiming training at the formation of professionally significant qualities of a teacher;
- a single, holistic process, consisting of two interdependent periods: training and education at the university, as well as further education, postgraduate education, which is built on the alternation of professional activities at school;

- actions aimed at the development of skills, the transfer of knowledge and the formation of a life position necessary for the implementation of professional skills.

Teacher training is interpreted by scientists as:

- teacher training based on educational activities, aimed at achieving a higher level of professional excellence and expanding the range of skills and abilities; as one of the forms of mastering progressive experience, the purpose of which is to increase the efficiency of the teacher's work;

- preparation of a teacher in an integral system of his education, creating motivational guidelines for self-improvement on the basis of innovative methodological structures leading to continuous self-education;

- improvement of professional training in the current conditions, when the teacher determines the level of formation of his professional and methodological knowledge and skills, planning his activities to improve training in accordance with the established initial level, the proposed areas and content of advanced training, self-control and self-control and self-correction of this activity.

Thus, the professional training of a teacher in the process of advanced training is an alternation of professional activities at school and educational activities, leading to the solution of pedagogical problems, to achieving a higher level of professional skills, to expanding the range of skills, to mastering progressive experience, to constant self-education.

Constant self-education of a teacher, when he plans his activities according to the initial level of formation of his professional and methodological knowledge and skills, the proposed areas and content of advanced training, exercises self-control and self-correction of his professional training, indicates the improvement of his professional training by the teacher, the increase in the efficiency of his work.

Conclusions. Thus, the participation of a teacher in the process of advanced training can be considered, firstly, as preparation for solving new problems in professional activities and socio-cultural activities, and secondly, as a special type

of educational and professional activity at all stages of becoming a specialist (adaptation, stabilization, transformations).

Of particular importance are the principles of advanced training (“updating education”, “systematic education”, “dynamism”, “polyvalence”, “intellectualization”), which ensure the implementation of the main principle of teaching orientation towards the comprehensive, harmonious development of the teacher’s personality and set a qualitatively new direction for his professional activities.

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